

MAKHMUDKHUJA BEKBUDI AND ENLIGHTENMENT

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Annotation: This article mentions most aspects of the activities of Mahmudkhoja Behbudi, a prominent representative of the Turkestan Jadid movement, an enlightened publicist, playwright. Schools and textbooks of Behbudi, newspapers and magazines, dramaturgy are discussed. The remarkable aspects of Behbudi's activity are analyzed.

Key words: Mahmudhoja Behbudi, jadid, "new method", education, school, newspaper.

Every era puts great tasks in front of the progressive intellectuals in the interests of the people, and they accept these tasks as their duty. The activity of the representatives of Uzbek literature and selfless enlighteners of the national renaissance, which occurred at the beginning of the last century, is a proof of this. During the years of independence, their life and rich literary heritage were studied, promoted, their names were restored, and their works were republished. Mahmudhoja Behbudi, a great enlightener, has a special place among such devotees of the nation.

The great enlightened writer, scholar and public figure Mahmudhoja Behbudi was born in 1875 in the city of Samarkand in the family of a mufti. The environment in the family of intellectuals led to the faster realization of his interest in literature, politics, and enlightenment. His father was a major specialist in Islamic jurisprudence and had written many books and treatises on the subject. This, in turn, had an impact on Mahmudhoja. Later, in one of his articles, he mentions that the work "Hidaya" (Comments on Islamic Law) taught by his father played an important role in his fate.

Mahmudhoja Behbudi is seriously engaged in political science along with literature and history. From newspapers and periodicals, he becomes closely acquainted with the political events taking place in the world. In order to go to Mecca, he began to learn Arabic and began to study the history and theory of Islam. In 1902, he went to Mecca and returned with the titles of Khoja and Mufti. Then he visited the cities of Kazan and Ufa and became interested in European culture. At that time, he cooperated with magazines and newspapers in Arabic spelling published in Kazan and Orenburg. A number of his articles began to appear in these magazines and newspapers. The promotion of the ideas of school, education, culture, enlightenment was in the center of these articles.

In particular, the Crimean-Tatar scholar Ismail Gaspirali (Gasperinsky) and the "Tarjumon" newspaper, where he was the editor-in-chief, raised M. Behbudi to the level of a great enlightener and the father of the Uzbek national struggle. The meeting with the members of the most influential party of cadets in Russia and their actions had a great influence on Behbudi's outlook. In 1912-1913, Behbudi founded the newspaper "Samarkand" and the magazine "Oyna" in Samarkand. In 1914, he again went to Turkey and Egypt, brought important books and textbooks from there, and started working on a new school program. However, he encountered various obstacles and was declared a "leader of the moderns" and a "modernist". Nevertheless, he supported the teachings of the Tatar thinker Ismail Gaspirali on enlightenment, started to implement similar works in his country, and soon won the respect of his people as an enlightener. In addition to being a highly cultured person who knew a number of Eastern and Western languages, he was also an indefatigable propagator of universal culture. Behbudi wrote more than two hundred articles and works in Uzbek and Persian-Tajik languages. For example, "Muntakhabi ul-jugrofi" - "Brief general geography" (1903), "Kitab-ul-atfol" - "Children's book" (1904), "Mukhtasari tarixul islam" - "Brief history of Islam" (1904), wrote textbooks and books such as "Practice of Islam" (1905), "Brief Geography of Russia" (1908). Since 1901, he has published "Gazette of the Turkistan region", "Taraqqi", "Khurshid", "Shuhrat", "Tujjor", "Osiyo", "Hurriyat", "Turon", "Sadoi Turkistan", "Ulug' Turkistan". His articles published in newspapers and magazines such as "Samarkand" and "Oyna" has gained the attention of people, especially young people.

As a writer, Behbudi created the drama "Padarkush" or the case of an uneducated child. In this drama published in Samarkand in 1913, he noted that young people (whether they belong to poor or rich families) should be educated and cultured. M. Behbudi's drama "Padarkush" or the plight of an uneducated child was written in 1911 and first published in 1912 in "Turon" newspaper. It was published as a book by 1913. After that, it was quickly performed on the stages of Samarkand, Bukhara and Tashkent theaters. While the drama is simple in its compositional structure, it is very comprehensive in terms of content and ideas. In particular, its character and movement, form and style were quite suitable for the requirements of this genre. And the characters in the drama live in two poles - with two different movements. On one side, there is a rich man, his son and his idols, and on the other side, the images of a teacher and an intellectual occupy an important place in revealing the idea of the work. Of course, Behbudi's growing reputation among the people was against the plans

and intentions of not only the leaders of the emirate, but also the Bolsheviks. Behbudi, who went on a foreign trip in 1919, was caught by them in Karshi and executed by order of Said Olimkhan.

S. Ayni wrote in connection with the tragic death of the scholar: "The name of the brave poet Behbudi is mentioned with respect in the Muslim East, because for 20 years he called all beings who knew the value of their consciousness and human value to fight for free life, light and enlightenment. came."

In conclusion, it should be said that the dream of our national progressives was to bring the Turkistan's out of decline, to take a place in the system of world culture along with advanced nations, and to introduce their culture to the world public. Their thoughts on cultural development and decline are closely analyzed directly with the issues of science, school, education, and education. They strove to develop Eastern and Western culture while preserving national characteristics in this field, and during their activities they considered science and education to be the first necessity for development, growth and development in the country. Because during their trips to foreign countries, the Jadids realized the difference between Western and Eastern countries and tried to explain to the people that the first direction of development is the necessity of science and technology. Unfortunately, the current situation and social system did not allow us to realize the noble goals set by our ancestors. For them, education, development of science, and national growth became a dream. As the main goal of today is to create the foundations of the Third Renaissance in Uzbekistan, as the President noted, "The time has come when the dreams of our great ancestors will come true. Their unique and unique scientific and spiritual heritage should become a vital program for us. This immortal heritage should always be with us and always give us strength and inspiration. First of all, we need to imbue the national education system with such a spirit."

References:

1. Bexbudiy M. Prepared for publication, compiler, foreword and author of comments - Professor BEGALI KOSIMOV. "Spirituality", 2006. 280 p. (Heroes of Independence).
2. Nusrat Thank you. "Jadid" novel. Publishing house "Publishing house". Tashkent, 2020.
3. Daslat Scientific Publishing House "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan". Tashkent, 2001.
4. Xujaev M. (2020) "MAHMUDKHUJA BEHBUDIY AS A LEADER OF JADID REFORMS," The Light of Islam: Vol. 2020: Iss. 3, Article <https://uzjournals.edu.uz/iiiau/vol2020/iss3/4>

5. Ibrahim, N. (2022). MAHMUDKHOJA BEHBUDI'S WORKS AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE. Journal of Youth Research, 1(2), 43-46.

